

Automated Fibre Placement of Ox-Ox CMCs

Ox-Ox CMCs

Continuous operation at 1000 °C – no TBCs

1/3rd density of Nickel superalloys

Low dielectric, low creep, low corrosion

~10% of Ni Superalloys
~4x higher than monolithic ceramics

Manual manufacture

High Cost

These items are being exported under the OGEL (Export of Dual-use items to EU Member States).
These items are being exported under the GEA001 license GBOGE2021/00939 covering Australia, Canada, Japan, New Zealand, Norway, Switzerland, including Liechtenstein and the USA

New Material - 3M Towpreg

- All Alumina: Nextel 610 tows + alumina matrix
- Room temperature stable
- Matrix contains <1% water and additives for tack (**12% total**)
- Stated width: 6.34 +/- **~1.2 mm**
- 40-45% fibre volume expected
- Max continuous temperature use = 1000 °C
- No recommended processing conditions

Outputs and Deliverables

Outputs

- Get the UK ready for a non-US Ox-Ox CMC
- Adaptation existing AFP equipment for CMCs
- Understand the relationship between key processing variables (KPVs) and the CMC
- Demonstrate benefits of automation – increased control and repeatability
- Assess the CMC-AFP supply chain

Deliverables

- Project report with processing parameters
- Summary project presentation

Objectives Completed
+ Semi Complex demonstrator

Machine Modifications

Feed rollers

Guide plate assembly
incl. driven feed shaft

Compaction roller

Cutting blades

Cutting anvils

Multiwinch system

Fibre guide tubes

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WP3 - AFP KPV Study

- 15 KPV samples
- 4 ply thickness (0.44 mm)
- Inspection using metrology arm
- Best parameters used to manufacture 16 ply thick demonstrator
- NDT also conducted on demonstrator

Wrinkle – 16 ply component

Before Autoclave

After Autoclave

After Sintering

	Preform	Consolidated laminate	Sintered laminate
Mean thickness (mm)	1.977	1.566	2.073
Maximum thickness (mm)	5.852	2.032	4.867
Minimum thickness (mm)	0.335	0.387	0.394
Standard deviation (mm)	0.246	0.125	0.534
Bulk factor	N/A	26%	-5%

Summary

- Core project has demonstrated Europe's first use of AFP-CMC
- KPV study completed
- 16 ply semi-complex panel manufactured
- Material width variation present (± 1.27 mm, 40% width)
- More heat is required for AFP layup than organic matrix composites
- CT scan and metrology reveal delaminations

Initial Trials: Single Courses

KPV Trials: Radius Study and Panel Manufacture

Autoclave + Sintering + CT Scan

AFP-CMC 2

Slit tape

Complex Demonstrator

Materials Characterisation

- Increased application over AFP-CMC 1
- Influence component for AFP-CMC 2
- Regular interaction with 3M

